

Formation Constants of some Trivalent Rare Earth Metal Complexes with *p,p'*-Bromo-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Anil

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Manuscript received 22 January 1990, revised 30 April 1991,
accepted 21 June 1991

THE present communication describes the potentiometric studies of complex formation by trivalent Pr, Nd, Sm and Gd with the Schiff base ligand *p,p'*-bromosulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil (*p,p'*-BSHNA). The study has been carried out in aqueous medium at different temperatures and ionic strengths using Calvin-Bjerrum¹ pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti².

Experimental

The Schiff base ligand *p,p'*-BSHNA was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity was checked by elemental analysis. The identity of the compound was also checked by comparing its ir spectrum with that of *p*-bromo-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil.

The rare earth metals were estimated by EDTA method⁴. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 *M* HClO₄ to avoid metal hydrolysis.

Procedure for pH-metric titrations involving titrations of known amount of the ligand (*p,p'*-BSHNA) containing known amount of HClO₄ in absence and in presence of known amount of metal ions at 25, 35 and 45° in aqueous solution maintaining a fixed ionic strength using NaClO₄ was the same as reported earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

Owing to very low concentration of the metal ion used, the formation of polynuclear complexes was considered to be unimportant. The metal curve showed departure from the ligand curve at pH much lower than the pH of hydrolysis of the metal ions⁶ and this suggests that the liberation of proton is due to chelation alone. The \bar{n} (metal-ligand formation number) was ~ 0.8 , which indicates 1 : 1 complexations. The metal-ligand and proton-ligand formation

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF *p,p'*-BSHNA AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTH

Temp. °C	<i>I</i> (NaClO ₄) <i>M</i>	H ⁺		Pr log <i>K</i> ₁	Nd log <i>K</i> ₁	Sm log <i>K</i> ₁	Gd log <i>K</i> ₁
		log <i>K</i> ₁	log <i>K</i> ₂				
25	0.1	10.00	7.50	7.95	8.75	10.00	8.30
35	0.1	9.30	7.00	6.85	7.25	8.85	8.65
	0.05	9.90	7.40	7.60	8.20	9.70	9.35
	0.01	10.45	7.86	8.26	9.16	10.57	9.72
	0.0	11.00	8.20	9.00	10.10	11.35	10.70
45	0.1	9.00	6.40	6.55	6.50	8.25	7.50

constants calculated by following the usual technique^{3,5} are given in Table 1.

The stoichiometric metal-ligand formation constants determined at 35° and at three different ionic strength (*I*=0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 *M* NaClO₄) were extrapolated to $\sqrt{I}=0$ to get the respective thermodynamic values (Table I). It is evident from the results that the formation constants decrease with increase in ionic strength of the medium. This is in agreement with the earlier observation⁷.

The stability order: Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}, is not uncommon in the case of lanthanide complexes⁸ and this may be due to the varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interactions of 4*f*-metal orbitals with the ligand field⁹. The effect of ligand structure on the stability constant values can be visualised by comparing the M-L stability constant values with those of some other related ligands as reported earlier¹⁰.

The general structural formula of the four ligand is

X=H, 5,6-Benzo; Y=H, Br

The stability constant values for the same M-L complexes follow the order: *p,p'*-bromosulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil (*p,p'*-BSHNA) > *p*-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil (*p*-SHNA) > *p,p'*-bromosulphonosalicylidene anil (*p,p'*-BSSA) > *p*-sulphonosalicylidene anil (*p*-SSA). In the case of salicylaldehyde-Schiff base system, the electrons on azomethine nitrogen is likely to be more involved in interaction with delocalised π -orbital system of the benzene nucleus. In the case of hydroxynaphthaldehyde-Schiff base system such interaction is however expected to be less due to relatively less aromaticity of the naphthalene nucleus. Hence the availability of electrons for donation by the azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion will be relatively less effected in the hydroxynaphthaldehyde-Schiff base system compared to the salicylaldehyde-Schiff

base system. This is also reflected by the literature value¹¹ of bond order in the case of enolate ions of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.67) and salicylaldehyde (1.5) and the same order of decreasing stability of the corresponding copper chelates.

It is also observed that compared to *p*-SHNA the stability value of M-L complexes is higher in the case of *p,p'*-BSHNA. This may be due to the presence of Br in the aromatic ring where it behaves more as an electron-releasing group via stronger mesomeric effect rather than electron-withdrawing group through inductive effect¹². Such effect may lead to an increase in the donor ability of nitrogen atom in *p,p*-BSHNA relative to that in *p*-SHNA and hence the stability value of M-L complexes increases. Similar situation prevails in complexes of *p,p'*-BSSA and *p*-SSA.

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